

Validation of a Surface-Element Interface Current Method for Boiling Water Reactor Assembly Calculations in the DRAGON5 Lattice Code

Raphaël Guasch^{1*}, Bowen Cui¹, Alain Hébert^{1,2}

¹Polytechnique Montréal, Montréal, Canada;

²newcleo SA, Via Giuseppe Galliano, 27, 10129 Torino TO, Italy

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803504

ABSTRACT

Boiling Water Reactors fuel assemblies represent an important challenge for lattice codes as they involve particularly heterogeneous fuel lattices. An ATRIUM-10-like BWR assembly is studied using the DRAGON5 lattice calculation code. A new implementation of the Interface Current *multicell* method compatible with *surface element* geometry definitions is presented. A direct SHEM-MOC calculation approach is used to validate the interface current solver as a possible self-shielding solution. Then, the interface current solver is used in a two-level flux calculation approach both as a self-shielding and a first-level flux solution. Numerical validation is performed by comparison with Serpent2. DRAGON5-Serpent2 differences on k_∞ and pin-by-pin fission rates are analyzed at zero-burnup. The *multicell* Interface Current solver is validated as an efficient self-shielding solution option and as a possible first level flux solver.

Keywords: Deterministic methods, Lattice calculations, Interface Currents, Reactor physics, BWR.

1. INTRODUCTION

The modeling of Boiling Water Reactor (BWR) fuel assemblies in the DRAGON5 lattice code [1] has been studied following recent Canadian interest in small modular BWRs [2]. Historically, DRAGON5 (D5) has been developed to study PWR and CANDU designs. The introduction of BWR-specific elements in lattice models has prompted this study. In fact, native geometry analysis modules (SYBILT:, NXT:) present some drawbacks when it comes to nested assembly geometries typically encountered in BWRs. This is due to the presence of moderating channel boxes and potential control mechanisms. Furthermore, the *tracking* modules available in DRAGON5 presented additional limitations which had to be circumvented to allow efficient BWR lattice calculations. Most notably, the *Interface Currents* method (IC) was adapted to *surface-element* geometries descriptions and is now available through the SALT: tracking module.

An ATRIUM-10-like BWR fuel assembly is modeled in nominal lower core conditions with the aim of validating a computational scheme suitable for burnup and multiphysics calculations. In order to do so, a zero-burnup calculation scheme is optimized to obtain the desired compromise between computational time and precision. A direct scheme based on the SHEM295 energy mesh and the Method of Characteristics (MOC) is defined in an initial "best-estimate" approach. The newly implemented *surface-element* IC method is validated as a possible solution for self-shielding calculations. Then, two 2-level schemes are introduced and validated. The first is based on a 295g *Collision Probability* (CP) calculation on a coarse geometry followed by a 26g MOC calculation on the reference geometry. In the second calculation scheme, the first-level CP calculation is replaced by a multicell flux solution. This first-level flux solution uses the newly implemented *surface-element* IC solver. The two-level IC+MOC scheme acts as additional validation of the newly implemented IC solver. DRAGON5 calculations are validated through a code-to-code comparison with the Serpent2 (S2) continuous energy Monte Carlo code [3].

*raphael.guasch@polymtl.ca

2. THEORY : BWR ASSEMBLY GEOMETRIES AND THE SURFACE-ELEMENT IC METHOD

The DRAGON5 lattice code has historically been developed to model PWR fuel assemblies or CANDU clusters. The geometry creation module (GEO:) and geometry analysis modules have thus been developed to suit these requirements. The GEO: module can be called recursively, allowing users to define nested geometries. In theory, there is no limitation to the number of nesting levels. Typical PWR and CANDU geometries only require 2 nesting levels of geometric description. Such geometries are supported in the SYBILT: (for IC and CP solutions) and NXT: (for CP and MOC solutions) tracking modules. However, BWR assemblies require a third nesting level in order to properly describe moderating channels and control crosses, if present. This type of geometry with three nests does not allow for a *multicell* IC solution available through the SYBILT: tracking module. It was foreseen that this would greatly limit the possibilities for efficient 2-level computational schemes in the context of BWR assembly geometries.

This led to the development of a *surface-element* IC method based on the SALT: tracking module. Three-nest geometries can thus be split into "cells" that represent sub-geometries. Collision probabilities are computed in each cell. This allows for the full CP matrix to be split into several subsystems. This reduces the number of regions in each system and the time required to invert the associated matrices. The flux calculation in each cell is coupled to its neighbors through a surface connectivity table that is automatically generated from the surfacic file generated by the G2S: geometry analysis module. This approach can be extended to non-native constructive solid geometries (CSG) generated by the external application GLOW [4].

In the current implementation, the interface currents computed at the boundaries between cells are limited to an isotropic description. The presented IC method is thus equivalent to a DP0 multicell solution [5] of the SYBILT: tracking module. Results for the validation of the newly implemented surface-element IC method in DRAGON5 are presented.

3. COMPUTATIONAL AND VALIDATION METHODS

3.1. Deterministic computational schemes

Lattice calculations require robust and efficient methods in order to generate condensed and homogenized cross sections for finite core applications. This implies that an optimized compromise must be found between accuracy, time and memory requirements. Direct "reference" and 2-level "optimized" computational schemes are now introduced.

3.1.1. One level computational schemes

The first computational scheme presented is based on a direct 295g MOC calculation. It makes use of the *Collision Probability* (CP) method at the self-shielding step and a precise Method of Characteristics (MOC) solution on a finely discretized geometry. This scheme will be referred to as the 1-level or direct MOC scheme. In this work, all MOC solutions involve cyclic trackings with specular boundary conditions. The step characteristic (SC), flat source approximation is used.

An alternative to the 1-level MOC scheme using a surface-element IC calculation at the self-shielding step is presented. This comparison between CP and IC methods will serve as a first result for the validation of the IC solver.

The main drawback of the direct MOC approach is the important computational time. For example, in DRAGON5 a direct 295g MOC calculation on the reference geometry (Fig. 1d) takes around 14 hours on 20 *openmp* parallel processes. In order to speed up the computation times, 2-level computational schemes must be considered.

Figure 1. Comparison of DRAGON5 calculation geometries: (a) Self-shielding (SSH) / First level flux calculation geometry (CP or IC), (b) Geometry with windmill coolant sectorization first level IC, (c) Geometry with sectorized Gd-loaded pins (MOC), (d) Reference flux calculation geometry with discretized moderator and sectorized fuel and coolant (MOC).

3.1.2. Two level computational schemes

The idea of splitting assembly flux calculations into two steps is based on the work of Vidal et al. [6] and is referred to as the "REL-2005" scheme. In its original form, it involves a multicell self-shielding step, followed by a multicell first level flux calculation step performed on a coarse meshing of the geometry. Both of the latter are performed on a fine energy mesh. Cross sections are condensed to a coarse structure. Lastly, a MOC calculation is performed on a finely meshed geometry in order to capture the spatial variations in the neutron flux and properly estimate pin-by-pin reaction rates.

In this work, four "REL-2005"-like calculation schemes are presented and compared. These schemes are based on self-shielding and first-level calculations performed on a coarse geometry (Figs. 1a or 1b) and a 295 energy groups structure. Self-shielding and first-level flux calculations are performed with either the CP or IC method. The first level cross sections are condensed from the 295g fine energy mesh to a 26g coarse structure. An SPH equivalence procedure is performed up to the 19th coarse group. The correction is not applied to the most thermal groups due to the presence of absorbing Gd causing numerical instabilities. The second part of the flux calculation involves a MOC calculation on a finely meshed geometry (Fig. 1d).

3.2. Spatial convergence of the MOC solution

The optimization of the MOC flux calculation geometry was performed by conducting a spatial convergence study on increasingly fine meshing parameters. In this work, 2 geometries have been selected and are presented in Figure 1. The effects of fuel sectorization and coolant discretization on the accuracy of MOC solution are assessed by comparing the k_{∞} and the pin-by-pin fission rates for increasingly fine geometries (Fig. 1c and 1d). It must be noted that, as the geometries are refined, the tracking parameters used need to be refined, too. The number of angles and line densities have been selected such that the maximum error between the region volumes computed analytically and from the tracking is 1%. This condition is met for 24 angles and 140.0 lines per cm in the "Sectorized Gd" geometry (Fig. 1c). For the tracking of the "Reference" geometry (Fig. 1d), the line density was increased to 150.0 lines per cm.

3.3. Validation methodology

An ATRIUM-10 BWR assembly is studied in nominal lower core conditions. A code-to-code deterministic-stochastic methodology is applied to numerically validate the DRAGON5 calculations. Reference results are obtained using the Serpent2 Monte Carlo code [3] converged with 2×10^5 particles and 5×10^3 cycles as suggested in [7]. The first 100 generations are discarded. Both DRAGON5 and Serpent2 calculations are based on the JEFF3.1.1 nuclear data evaluation.

An assessment of DRAGON5 capabilities is performed under zero-burnup conditions. Best estimate calculations are performed and compared with the Serpent2 results. The metrics used to assess the precision of our calculations are the difference in the eigenvalue (Δk_∞) and the relative differences on the pin-by-pin fission rates. This first step is carried out using a direct MOC approach for which either the CP or surface-element IC methods are used for the self-shielding step.

Two-level flux calculation schemes are then considered as an extension to the validation of the surface-element IC solver. All combinations of IC and CP solvers for the self-shielding and first level flux calculation steps are considered.

In all approaches, the anisotropic orders considered to represent scattering cross sections are :

1. Isotropic P_0 , with transport correction (*Correction de TRANsport* in french, denoted CTRA),
2. Linear anisotropic expansion (P_1),
3. Cubic anisotropic expansion (P_3).

In order for a DRAGON5 computational scheme to be considered validated, the criteria set are :

1. ± 250 pcm DRAGON5 - Serpent2 difference in k_∞ at zero-burnup.
2. Maximum 1% RMS difference in pin-wise fission rates.
3. Maximum $\pm 2\%$ difference in pin-by-pin fission rates.

The reaction rates are condensed to a 2-group structure in which the division between the "thermal" and "fast" domains is set at 0.625 eV. In order to allow for a code-to-code comparison, the reaction rates computed with DRAGON5 and Serpent2 have been normalized to the number of fissile pin cells in the problem geometry. It should be noted that DRAGON5 fission rates have been "unfolded" along the diagonal symmetry before comparison with the Serpent2 model.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND VALIDATION OF ZERO-BURNUP CALCULATIONS

The following section presents the validation of DRAGON5 BWR assembly calculations, in zero-burnup conditions. The RSE self-shielding method available in DRAGON5 [8] is selected. First, we present a short study of geometry discretization for the MOC flux calculation. Then, direct calculation schemes using the CP and IC methods in self-shielding calculations are compared. Lastly, two-level schemes are considered. The impact of using either the CP or IC method to obtain the first-level flux solution is assessed. The speedup factor gained by switching to a two-level scheme is also assessed.

4.1. Geometry discretization for the MOC solution

The choice of an appropriate geometry discretization for a MOC solution is crucial to properly estimate pin-by-pin reaction rates. Table I presents a DRAGON5 - Serpent2 comparison obtained using the CP method at the self-shielding step and a P_3 MOC solution on increasingly fine geometries. The latter are presented in Figures 1c, and 1d.

Table I. D5-S2 differences on k_∞ , relative RMS and MAX differences on fast an thermal fission rates, CP self-shielding solution and P_3 MOC. Comparison performed on increasingly fine geometries.

Geometry	Δk_∞ (pcm)	Δ_{RMS,τ_f}		Δ_{MAX,τ_f}		Total time
		fast	thermal	fast	thermal	
"Sectorized Gd"	-239	0.19%	0.74%	0.58%	1.74%	10h06
"Reference"	-89	0.17%	0.71%	0.50%	1.58%	13h35

This survey of geometric discretization options shows that azimuthal sectorization of Gd bearing fuel pins is necessary to meet the $\pm 2\%$ condition set on maximum relative errors between D5 and S2 fission

rates. Furthermore, it was found that the azimuthal sectorization of all fuel pins significantly improved the difference in k_∞ and in fission rates. For this reason, the "Reference" discretization shown in Figure 1d was selected to carry out the rest of this study.

4.2. Validation of the IC solver for self-shielding in direct MOC schemes

The validation of calculations with fresh fuel composition is first performed using the direct MOC approach. The CP and IC solvers are used at the self-shielding step and compared.

Table II presents the differences in k_∞ and the relative RMS differences in the fast and thermal fission rates between DRAGON5 and Serpent2. The self-shielding step is performed with the CP or IC solvers. The MOC calculations were performed with varying scattering orders. The isotropic cases with a transport correction (P_0 +CTRA) give the best results in terms of k_∞ . However, their associated errors on fission rates do not comply with the validation criteria set. The P_1 cases provide satisfying precision in fission rates but show the greatest D5-S2 differences on k_∞ out of all 6 test cases. Lastly, the P_3 scattering cases provided the best estimates considering both Δk_∞ and fission rates.

The seemingly better precision of P_1 cases on fission rates could be explained by more spatial compensation due to the choice of reaction rates normalization. Only comparing fission rates and k_∞ does not allow to fully analyze this result.

Figure 2 shows the map of the differences between D5 and S2 in pin-by-pin fast (a) and thermal (b) fission rates for the IC + P_3 MOC case. The Gd-loaded fuel pins systematically present underestimations of thermal fission rates, which are compensated by overestimation in neighboring UOX fuel. The maximum error shown is an underestimation of -1.58% in low enrichment UOX pins located in the corners. All presented P_1 and P_3 cases are within the $\pm 2\%$ bounds.

Table II. D5-S2 differences on k_∞ , relative RMS and MAX differences on fast and thermal fission rates and time spent at the self-shielding step for direct MOC calculation schemes.

SSH sol.	ANIS	Δk_∞ (pcm)	Δ_{RMS,τ_f}		Δ_{MAX,τ_f}		Total time
			fast	thermal	fast	thermal	
IC	P_0 +CTRA	55	0.41%	0.93%	1.20%	2.51%	3h48
CP	P_0 +CTRA	88	0.39%	0.93%	1.13%	2.51%	5h28
IC	P_1	-225	0.21%	0.42%	0.48%	1.11%	4h39
CP	P_1	-208	0.21%	0.43%	0.48%	1.11%	6h20
IC	P_3	-106	0.17%	0.70%	0.50%	1.58%	12h12
CP	P_3	-89	0.17%	0.71%	0.50%	1.58%	13h35

The results presented in Table II and Figure 2 show that the newly implemented IC solver can be successfully validated as a potential solver for self-shielding applications. Switching from a CP to an IC solution for the self-shielding solution represents a ≈ 5.3 speedup factor in the time spent in the self-shielding calculation.

4.3. Validation of the IC solver in 2-level schemes

The new surface-element multicell solver (IC) is now used to perform a first-level flux calculation on the fine 295 groups SHEM mesh and on a coarse geometry. In the "windmills" cases, the coolant is sectorized as shown in Fig. 1b. Table III shows the differences on k_∞ along with the relative RMS and MAX differences in fast and thermal fission rates. All combinations of IC and CP solvers at the self-shielding and first-level steps are presented. Regarding the scattering law, the same 3 options are kept

Figure 2. D5-S2 comparison of normalized fission rates in the fast (a) and thermal (b) energy groups. D5 results are obtained with the direct MOC scheme with P_3 scattering on 295 groups, using RSE+ IC self-shielding options.

from the previous direct calculations.

Judging from the results presented in Table III, it can be seen that using the IC method as a first-level flux solution requires a coolant windmill sectorization to significantly improve its precision.

The differences between schemes that use IC or CP as a first-level flux solution are interpreted to be due to the limitation of the surface element IC method to a DP0 (isotropic) expansion of the flux currents at the interfaces between cells. As seen by the IC "windmills" cases, this effect can be mitigated by introducing more outer surfaces around each cell. This is recommended to better approximate the neutron current at the cell's interfaces. It should be stressed that when using a P_3 scattering order, both schemes using the IC method can be considered valid in terms of Δk_∞ , Δ_{RMS,τ_f} and Δ_{MAX,τ_f} . It should be noted that using a higher order representation of scattering is required to guarantee a strict $\pm 250 pcm$ agreement with S2. This is particularly the case when using IC at the first level.

The maps of relative differences in the fast and thermal pin-by-pin fission rates for the IC+IC+ P_3 MOC case are presented in Figures 3 (a) and (b). The IC "windmill" discretization is used. The RMS difference for the thermal fission rates is 0.54% in the IC+IC+ P_3 MOC case instead of 0.50% in the direct IC+ P_3 MOC calculation. The MAX difference in thermal fission rates is an over estimation by 1.26% in highly enriched UOX cells neighboring 3 Gd-bearing pins.

The time spent computing the 2 flux levels when using the CP+ P_3 MOC and IC "windmills"+ P_3 MOC approaches is around 4600s. This is reduced to around 3600s when using the IC+ P_3 MOC solution. Compared to the direct P_3 MOC solution, switching to a two-level approach using the IC method allows for a speed-up factor of flux calculations of around 8 to 11, depending on the choice of IC discretization.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A new multicell IC method has been developed in the SALT: module of DRAGON5. This method is based on the surface-element description of geometries. The present work has shown that it can be used to perform efficient self-shielding calculations yielding results comparable to the CP method, both in terms of k_∞ and pin-by-pin fission rates. The speedup factor gained by switching from CP to IC to perform self-shielding calculations is around 5.3.

Table III. D5-S2 differences on k_∞ , relative RMS differences on fast and thermal fission rates for 2-level calculation schemes.

SSH sol.	1st lvl. sol.	ANIS	Δk_∞ (pcm)	Δ_{RMS,τ_f}		Δ_{MAX,τ_f}		Total time
				fast	thermal	fast	thermal	
IC	IC (windmills)	P_0 +CTRA	-34	0.43%	0.94%	1.25%	2.42%	1h32
IC	IC	P_0 +CTRA	-62	0.42%	0.94%	1.23%	2.40%	1h00
CP	IC (windmills)	P_0 +CTRA	-1	0.41%	0.94%	1.18%	2.42%	2h51
CP	IC	P_0 +CTRA	-29	0.40%	0.94%	1.16%	2.39%	2h42
IC	CP	P_0 +CTRA	44	0.41%	0.93%	1.19%	2.32%	1h12
CP	CP	P_0 +CTRA	77	0.39%	0.93%	1.12%	2.32%	2h59
IC	IC (windmills)	P_1	-272	0.25%	0.46%	0.56%	1.07%	1h38
IC	IC	P_1	-309	0.24%	0.53%	0.52%	1.12%	1h06
CP	IC (windmills)	P_1	-256	0.25%	0.46%	0.56%	1.12%	2h59
CP	IC	P_1	-293	0.24%	0.53%	0.52%	1.12%	2h48
IC	CP	P_1	-233	0.23%	0.53%	0.51%	1.15%	1h22
CP	CP	P_1	-217	0.23%	0.53%	0.51%	1.16%	3h06
IC	IC (windmills)	P_3	-198	0.20%	0.65%	0.54%	1.25%	2h24
IC	IC	P_3	-230	0.20%	0.77%	0.55%	1.78%	1h45
CP	IC (windmills)	P_3	-182	0.21%	0.66%	0.54%	1.25%	3h48
CP	IC	P_3	-214	0.20%	0.77%	0.55%	1.79%	3h31
IC	CP	P_3	-154	0.19%	0.77%	0.55%	1.79%	2h03
CP	CP	P_3	-139	0.19%	0.77%	0.55%	1.79%	3h51

(a) D5-S2 (%), fast fission rates.

(b) D5-S2 (%), thermal fission rates.

 Figure 3. D5-S2 comparison of normalized fission rates in the fast (a) and thermal (b) energy groups. D5 results are obtained with an isotropic 295-groups first level IC calculation (with windmill coolant discretization), followed by MOC with P_3 scattering on 26 groups. RSE+ IC self-shielding options.

Furthermore, 2-level flux calculations can now be performed using the newly implemented surface element multicell method as a first-level flux solution, provided that a P_3 scattering order is selected. When doing so, it is recommended to introduce a “windmill” coolant sectorization in order to maximize the number of cell interfaces. Implementing a DP1 (linear) interface current expansion [5] is expected to yield results closer to the CP solution while conserving the advantageous computational time.

Although some precision on pin-by-pin fission rates and k_∞ is lost in the two-level approach, the results presented remain within the validation criteria set. This 2-level approach has helped reduce the total time spent in the flux solution by a factor of 11 when using and IC+IC+ P_3 MOC approach.

This newly implemented method and its associated calculation schemes open up new possibilities to perform more efficient BWR assembly calculations in the DRAGON5 lattice code. Future work will focus on validating such two-level schemes on different BWR fuel bundle benchmarks for multiphysics and burnup evolution calculations.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work received support from the Natural Science and Engineering Research Council of Canada under grant ALLRP 586456-2023.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Hébert. “DRAGON5 and DONJON5, the contribution of École Polytechnique de Montréal to the SALOME platform.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 87**, pp. 12–20 (2016). Special Issue of The 3rd International Conference on Physics and Technology of Reactors and Application.
- [2] “New reactor facility projects.” (2025). URL <https://www.cnsccsn.gc.ca/eng/reactors/power-plants/new-reactor-facilities>.
- [3] J. Leppänen, M. Pusa, T. Viitanen, V. Valtavirta, and T. Kaltiaisenaho. “The Serpent Monte Carlo code: Status, development and applications in 2013.” *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, pp. 142–150 (2015). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306454914004095>. Joint International Conference on Supercomputing in Nuclear Applications and Monte Carlo 2013, SNA + MC 2013. Pluri- and Trans-disciplinarity, Towards New Modeling and Numerical Simulation Paradigms.
- [4] D. Manzione and A. Hébert. “GLOW: Newcleo’s Application for Supporting Lattice Transport Calculations in DRAGON5.” In *Proceedings of PHYSOR2026* (Submitted 2025).
- [5] A. Hébert. *Applied Reactor Physics*. Presses internationales Polytechnique (2020).
- [6] J.-F. Vidal, O. Litaize, D. Bernard, A. Santamarina, C. Vaglio-Gaudard, and T. N. Tran. “New Modelling of LWR Assemblies using the APOLLO2 Code Package.” In *Proceedings of MC+SNA 2007* (2007).
- [7] M. Hursin, P. Mala, A. Vasiliev, F. Hakim, Y. Liu, S. Choi, and S. Kochunas. “Comparison of CASMO-5, MPACT and Serpent 2 for the modeling of advanced BWR lattices.” In *Proceedings of the international conference on physics of reactors - PHYSOR 2022* (2022).
- [8] A. Hébert. “A General Formulation of the Resonance Spectrum Expansion Self-Shielding Method.” *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, pp. 1–14 (2024). URL <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00295639.2024.2375908>.